

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP) for AIOSAT

- Instructions and footnotes in blue must not appear in the text.
- For options [in square brackets]: the option that applies must be chosen.
- For fields in [grey in square brackets] (even if they are part of an option as specified in the previous item): enter the appropriate data.

Introduction

This Horizon 2020 DMP template has been designed to be applicable to any Horizon 2020 project that produces, collects or processes research data. You should develop a single DMP for your project to cover its overall approach. However, where there are specific issues for individual datasets (e.g. regarding openness), you should clearly spell this out.

[Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020](#) are available in the Online Manual.

FAIR data management

In general terms, your research data should be 'FAIR', that is findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. These principles precede implementation choices and do not necessarily suggest any specific technology, standard, or implementation-solution.

This template is not intended as a strict technical implementation of the FAIR principles, it is rather inspired by FAIR as a general concept.

More information about FAIR:

[FAIR data principles \(FORCE11 discussion forum\)](#)

[FAIR principles \(article in Nature\)](#)

Structure of the template

The template is a set of questions that you should answer with a level of detail appropriate to the project.

It is not required to provide detailed answers to all the questions in the first version of the DMP that needs to be submitted by month 6 of the project. Rather, the DMP is intended to be a living document in which information can be made available on a finer level of granularity through updates as the implementation of the project progresses and when significant changes occur. Therefore, DMPs should have a clear version number and include a timetable for updates. As a minimum, the DMP should be updated in the context of the periodic evaluation/assessment of the project. If there are no other periodic reviews envisaged within the grant agreement, an update needs to be made in time for the final review at the latest.

In the following the main sections to be covered by the DMP are outlined. At the end of the document, Table 1 contains a summary of these elements in bullet form.

This template itself may be updated as the policy evolves.

Project¹ Number: [776425]

Project Acronym: [AIOSAT]

Project title: [Autonomous Indoor Outdoor SAfety Tracking system]

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

The objective of WP1 and WP7 Activities for the management, exploitation, dissemination and communication of results is to ensure the appropriate measures to exploit, disseminate and communicate the main results derived from the project.

This deliverable entitled as Data Management Plan (DMP) is a document which provides an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used by the members of the consortium with regard to the data generated through the life of the project.

The DMP will be released in compliance with the Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP template, provided by the European Commission in the Participant Portal.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Change
00.01	16.03.2018	▪ Initial version
00.02	20.03.2018	▪ Second subversion without the Data Protection paragraphs
00.03	26.03.2018	▪ Third subversion with the first complete draft
01.00	30.03.2018	▪ First stable version to be submitted

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2 INTRODUCTION

AIOSAT is a Horizon 2020 project participating funded by GSA. This project is part of the Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data Programme in H2020. The goal of the program is to foster access to data generated in H2020 projects.

Open Access refers to a practice of giving online access to all scholarly disciplines information that is free of charge to the end-user. In this way data becomes re-usable and the benefit of public investment in the research will be improved.

As described in **Figure 2**, the EC provided a document with guidelines for projects participants in the pilot. The guidelines address aspects like research data quality, sharing and security. According to the guidelines, projects participating will need to develop a Data Management Plan.

The purpose of the DMP is to provide an overview of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used by the Consortium with regard to the project research data. The DMP is not a fixed document but will evolve during the lifespan of the project.

The DMP covers the complete research data life cycle of the AIOSAT project. It describes the types of research data that will be generated during the project, the strategies on research data preservation and the provision on access rights. The research data should be “FAIR”, that is findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. These principles precede implementation choices and do not necessarily suggest any specific technology, standard or implementation solution.

In the context of research funding, open access requirements do not imply an obligation to publish results. The decision to publish is entirely up to the grant beneficiaries. Open access becomes an issue only if publication is chosen as a means of dissemination. Moreover, open access does not affect the decision to exploit research results commercially, e.g. through patenting. The decision on whether to publish through open access must come after the more general decision on whether to publish directly or to first seek protection.

The policy for Data Sharing in AIOSAT project is sketched in **Figure 1**, which includes different access levels for consortium members and for external users:

- Data Sharing and Access for Project Partners: all the information and research data related to the AIOSAT project will be shared through a **Sharepoint** Private Site to which only project partners can access.
- Data Sharing and Access for External users (Open Access):
 - Project **Website** (www.aiosat.eu): will be a key in supporting the project communication to the general public and the project stakeholders during the project lifetime.
 - **Zenodo** Repository: this repository will host the Open Access Research Data both during the project lifetime and after the project ending.

More information concerning the project website and the sharepoint can be found in Deliverables D7.3 and D7.4 from that project, which will be published in the website once approved.

The repository ZENODO has been chosen as the main repository to store, classify and provide Open Access to the stored data objects originated within the AIOSAT project frame.

Zenodo (zenodo.org) is an open, dependable repository for all of scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format. The main features of ZENODO that makes it a suitable tool for data sharing and preserving are:

- Zenodo is linked to Horizon2020 projects and all results are immediately linked to OpenAIRE and the EC portal.
- Share and link research: Zenodo provides a rich interface which enables linking research outputs to datasets and funding information. All open content is harvestable via OAI-PMH by third parties.
- Supports versioning: Via a top-level DOI you can support all the different versions of a file.
- Trusted, reliable, safe: Data is stored at CERN, which has considerable knowledge and experience operating large scale digital repositories. Data files and metadata are kept in multiple online and offline copies.
- Reviewing: Research materials can set to share with reviewers only, if needed.

Figure 1. AIOSAT data sharing policy

29.3 Open access to research data

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action ('**data**'), the beneficiaries must:

- (a) deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:
 - (i) the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications as soon as possible;
 - (ii) other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the '**data management plan**' (see Annex 1);
- (b) provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data if the achievement of the action's main objective, as described in Annex 1, would be jeopardised by

—

making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.

29.4 Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the Agency logo and EU emblem

Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- (a) display the Agency logo;
- (b) display the EU emblem, and
- (c) include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European GNSS Agency under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776425”.

When displayed together with another logo, the logo and emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the logo and emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency or the Commission.

This does not however give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the logo and emblem (or any similar trademark or logo), either by registration or by any other means.

Figure 2. H2020 Open Data Access from H2020 rules

3 DATA SUMMARY

The system to be created in AIOSAT aims to collect multisensored data for positioning of firefighters vehicle and person involved in a safety emergency. The collection of data is intended, at last, to visualize the position and to validate the functioning according to the requirements and scenarios defined in D2.1

The preliminary and simplified architecture of the nodes to be deployed as first responders is shown in next figure.

Figure 3. preliminary node architecture

Figure 3 presents that there are 3 main kind of data to compute the position:

- Inertial movement Unit (accelerations, gyroscopes and magnetometers)
- GNSS data
- RF Data

In every case, the template of datasets from partners acquiring and sharing these data will cover “Origin of the data”, “expected size”, “format”, “reusing of data”.

Every dataset and working document will be properly referenced to a version control number, where major versions are attained only when sending them for a milestone of the task.

The types and formats of data within the project frame include the following:

- Laboratory data: datasets (*.txt, *.doc, *.docx, *.xls, *.xlsx), multimodal measurements (*.txt, *.doc, *.docx, *.xls, *.xlsx), numerical data (*.XX), qualitative data (*.txt, *.doc, *.docx), data statistics (*.xls, *.xlsx), images (*.jpg, *.png, *.jpeg, *.tiff), videos (*.avi, *.mov, animated GIF), geographical information (*.kml, *.gpx).
- Fusion data: statistics (*.xls, *.xlsx), graphs (*.ogg, *.xls, *.xlsx), bibliography (*.enl), code and executables (*.rpm, *.exe, *.c, *.cpp, *.py, *.java)
- Scientific texts: manuscripts and reports (*.doc, *.docx, *.pdf), publications (*.doc, *.docx, *.pdf), conference proceedings (*.doc, *.docx, *.pdf), conference presentations and posters (*.ppt, *.pptx, *.pdf), books and theses (*.doc, *.docx, *.pdf).
- Dissemination material: leaflets and fact-sheets (*.pdf), images (*.jpg, *.png, *.jpeg, *.tiff), animated images (*.gif), videos (*.mp4), social network publications and website (*.html), presentations and templates (*.ppt, *.pptx, *.pdf).
- Management documents: deliverables (*.doc, *.docx, *.pdf), patents (*.doc, *.docx, *.pdf).

4 FAIR DATA

4.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE

METADATA PROVISION

ZENODO repository offers the possibility to assign several metadata to all uploads, in order to make the content findable. The tags ZENODO offers are:

- Publication type (journal article, presentation, book, thesis...etc.).
- Title, authors, affiliation.
- Description of the content.
- Communities that the data belong to.
- Grants which have funded the research.
- Identifiers (DOI, ISSN, PubMed ID, URLs...etc.).
- Contributors.
- References.

IDENTIFIABILITY OF DATA

Zenodo assigns all publicly available uploads a digital object identifier (DOI) to make the upload easily and uniquely citeable. If the upload already has a DOI assigned, it can be detailed in the metadata provision.

All data generated under the AIOSAT project will acknowledge the grant in the following way “*Results incorporated in this project received funding from the European GNSS Agency under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776425*”, and will automatically be associated to the project via OpenAIRE portal.

KEYWORDS

All uploads will include a group of relevant keywords in order to facilitate the identification of the results.

CLEAR VERSIONING

Zenodo repository provides a new feature to handle versioning: DOI versioning allows to edit/update the record’s files after they have been published, cite a specific version of a record and cite all of versions of a record.

When an upload is published on Zenodo for the first time, Zenodo registers two DOIs:

- a DOI representing the **specific version** of the record.
- a DOI representing **all of the versions** of the record.

Afterwards, a DOI is registered for every new version of the same upload.

4.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

WHICH DATA WILL BE MADE OPENLY AVAILABLE

Scientific Publications

Article 29.2 of the model grant agreement sets out detailed legal requirements on open access to scientific publications: under horizon 2020, each beneficiary must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. Therefore, all the scientific publications originated by the AIOSAT project will be made openly accessible; gold or green Open Access Publishing.

There is a list of journals with that status in “www.ieee.org/go/journals” following the description “IEEE Hybrid Open Access Journals”.

Other Research Data

Additionally, any other research data or information set us publishable will also be made openly accessible. However, any dissemination data linked to exploitable results will not be put into the public domain if they compromise their commercialization or have inadequate protection.

HOW THE DATA WILL BE MADE AVAILABLE

The open access mandate comprises 2 steps: depositing publications in repositories and providing open access to them.

The AIOSAT project will fulfill these two steps by uploading the data to the Zenodo repository.

METHODS OR SOFTWARE TOOLS NEEDED TO ACCESS THE DATA

As a general rule, the format of the data deposited in Zenodo repository will enable the access to them through standard software tools like Adobe Acrobat Reader or Microsoft Office Package.

For data formats that cannot be opened using standard software tools, reliable information on the tools required to validate the results will be provided with the data.

HOW ACCESS WILL BE PROVIDED IN CASE THERE ARE ANY RESTRICTIONS

As detailed in previous sections, any dissemination data linked to exploitable results will not be put into the public domain if they compromise their commercialization or have inadequate protection. In this case, the scientific committee of AIOSAT will individually analyze and decide on the particular access and time restrictions for each result.

4.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

AIOSAT will encourage the use of standard vocabularies for all data types present in the data sets to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability. In case this is not possible for a specific data set, project partners will provide mappings to more commonly used vocabulary.

4.4 DATA RE-USE

HOW THE DATA WILL BE LICENCED TO PERMIT THE WIDEST REUSE POSSIBLE

Data re-use is subjected to the license under which it is deposited on Zenodo. The Steering committee will decide on the specific license that applies to each data deposited, taking into account the exploitability of the results.

WHEN THE DATA WILL BE MADE AVAILABLE FOR RE-USE.

The data will be available for re-use immediately after deposition on Zenodo Repository.

Scientific publications will be uploaded to Zenodo as soon as they are published by the editorial and, at the latest, six months after publication.

Other research data not linked to scientific publication will be uploaded to Zenodo following the instructions of the Managing team.

THIRD-PARTIES AND RE-USABILITY

The data uploaded to Zenodo, as they are deposited on a free-access base, can be re-used by third parties.

DATA QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCESSES

Data quality assurance is performed by the Zenodo Repository. In particular, for each file uploaded, two independent MD5 checksums are stored. One checksum is stored by Invenio, and used to detect changes to files made from outside of Invenio. The other checksum is stored by EOS, and used for automatic detection and recovery of file corruption on disks.

LENGTH OF TIME FOR WHICH THE DATA WILL REMAIN RE-USABLE

All the files uploaded to Zenodo will remain re-usable for the lifetime of the repository, that is the lifetime of the CERN.

In case of closure of Zenodo, the best efforts will be made in order to preserve the data in an alternative repository.

5 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

5.1 COSTS FOR MAKING DATA FAIR

The costs for making data FAIR are mainly those related to the cost of Open Access to Scientific Publications, as the use of Zenodo Repository is free of charge.

Costs related to open access to research data in Horizon 2020 are eligible for reimbursement during the duration of the project under the conditions defined in the H2020 Grant Agreement.

5.2 RESPONSIBILITIES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT IN AIOSAT PROJECT

Any member of the Consortium can upload content in the repository.

5.3 COSTS AND POTENTIAL VALUE OF LONG TERM PRESERVATION

Long term preservation of AIOSAT open access research data will be based on Zenodo Repository, which is free of charge.

The Steering committee of AIOSAT will decide on long term preservation of Research data associated to exploitable results. This will be done during the project lifetime and based on the protection strategy followed by the consortium.

6 DATA SECURITY

6.1 DATA STORAGE

6.1.1 SHAREPOINT

Microsoft uses some of the strongest, most secure encryption protocols in the industry to provide a barrier against unauthorized access to data. When data is at rest two types of encryption are used: disk encryption and file encryption. On disk encryption level a BitLocker is used to secure data and on file encryption level every file is secured with its own key that uses Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) with 256-bit keys, which is a Federal Information Processing Standard (FIPS) 140-2 compliant.

6.1.2 ZENODO

DATA STORAGE

All files uploaded to Zenodo are stored in CERN's EOS service in an 18 petabytes disk cluster. Each file copy has two replicas located on different disk servers.

For each file two independent MD5 checksums are stored. One checksum is stored by Invenio, and used to detect changes to files made from outside of Invenio. The other checksum is stored by EOS, and used for automatic detection and recovery of file corruption on disks.

Zenodo may, depending on access patterns in the future, move the archival and/or the online copy to CERN's offline long-term tape storage system CASTOR in order to minimize long-term storage costs.

EOS is the primary low latency storage infrastructure for physics data from the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) and CERN currently operates multiple instances totalling 150+ petabytes of data with expected growth rates of 30-50 petabytes per year. CERN's CASTOR system currently manages 100+ petabytes of LHC data which are regularly checked for data corruption.

Invenio provides an object store like file management layer on top of EOS which is in charge of e.g. version changes to files.

METADATA STORAGE

Metadata and persistent identifiers in Zenodo are stored in a PostgreSQL instance operated on CERN's Database on Demand infrastructure with 12-hourly backup cycle with one backup sent to tape storage once a week. Metadata is in addition indexed in an Elasticsearch cluster for fast and powerful searching. Metadata is stored in JSON format in PostgreSQL in a structure described by versioned JSONSchemas. All changes to metadata records on Zenodo are versioned, and happening inside database transactions.

6.2 DATA TRANSFER

All data exchanges will be performed throughout web services based on HTTPS protocol (both Sharepoint and Zenodo fulfil this condition).

7 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

Partners have established a legal framework for the Project in order to provide clear regulations for issues within the consortium related to Results and Intellectual Property Ownership, Confidential Information, Open Source issues, Standard contributions, and Access Rights to Background and Foreground along the duration of the Project and any other matters of the consortium's interest. The AIOSAT consortium has adopted a Consortium Agreement (CA) under the DESCA 2020 Model Consortium Agreement. Although the agreed CA is a base and stable document, it may be modified during the Project duration to take into account any updated consensus on the project results.

The CA also covers full rights and responsibilities of participants during the project in respect of the confidentiality of information disclosed by the Partners, as well as the publication and communication of information. Moreover, the CA provides additional rules to ensure effective dissemination of the results. Settlements of internal disputes and of course Intellectual Property (IP) arrangements are part of the CA as well.

Any knowledge, information, data and/or IPR generated before the effective date of the CA (i.e. background) shall remain with the respective Party providing such background to the Project. Any result generated by a Party after the said date, during and within the scope of the Project (i.e. Result), whether or not it qualifies for Intellectual Property Right (IPR) protection, shall vest in the Party that generated such Result. Any jointly generated Result will be jointly owned. The rights and obligations associated to such jointly generated Result will be regulated in the CA, but in any event each joint owner contributing to the cost of such jointly generated Result shall enjoy an unrestricted right to freely use and exploit such jointly generated Result. Throughout the execution of the project, all Partners will continuously contribute to the identification of Results that may qualify for IPR protection and will act with the aim of achieving a meaningful outcome for the community following completion of the project.

In case certain results are identified to be essential for the future business opportunities of the involved partners, the necessary steps will be taken to protect such results accordingly. The patenting and other protective measure procedures will proceed along the regulations set forth in the CA.

The IP terms and conditions during the cooperation of AIOSAT will be, *a priori*, based on a royalty free basis. After completion of the project (i.e. during exploitation) access rights to background and to Results may require fair and reasonable compensation with non-discriminatory conditions, subject to agreement amongst the parties and reflected in the CA.

All access rights needed for the execution of the project and following completion of the project will be granted on a non-exclusive basis, will be worldwide and in principle, will not contain the right to grant sub-license(s). The CA will further regulate rights and obligations for affiliated entities of a party, where those shall enjoy the same access rights conditions as the party participating in the project, and where such affiliated entities will need to grant requested access rights to other parties if those are needed during execution and/or following completion of Lase4surf.

The CA also provides additional rules on the introduction, pursuant to notification, of background that has been made available under controlled license terms, e.g. so-called open source licenses. To the extent required for proper use of software results, sub-licensing rights on software results are regulated by the CA if it is in the best interest of the project dissemination, where such sub-licensing rights shall not be in a manner where the so licensed software results would be subject to controlled license terms. Means to make software results available to the other parties or to the public are part of the CA.

7.1 IPR MODELS

Three possible models have been considered during the proposal preparation phase and will be estimated during the project execution phases. The current consensus of the consortium is the retention of title, ownership and exploitation rights of the results and IPR generated on an individual per partner basis as the preferred option, although other no binding options will be explored.

Results - Foreground and IP shall be owned by the project partner carrying out the work leading to such Foreground and IP. If any Foreground and IP is created jointly by at least two project partners and it is not possible to distinguish between the contributions of each of the project partners, such work will be jointly owned by the contributing project partners. The same shall apply if, in the course of carrying out work on the project, an invention is made having two or more contributing parties contributing to it, and it is not possible to separate the individual contributions. Such joint inventions and all related patent applications shall be jointly owned by the contributing parties. Alternative models to be explored, on the basis of unanimous agreement, are:

- *Joint Ownership and Exploitation:* The AIOSAT partners will register title and jointly share the exploitation rights of the project foreground based on the relative share of Person Month effort dedicated to the project.
- *Per Work Package or Tasks Ownership and Exploitation:* In this case, each partner or sub group of partners involved in individual tasks will register title and exploit the results of their own Work Package.
- *Combined Approach to Title and Exploitation:* In this case the AIOSAT partners will register title in the foreground and IPR in line with their own Foreground and IPR policy.

7.2 IPR OFFICER AND THE AUDITING AND MANAGEMENT OF GENERATED DATA - RESULTS AND IPR.

The AIOSAT proposal has appointed a specialist on IPR. The role of the IPR Officer (IPO) will be to act as an honest broker with the Research and Management staff of the project and provide an objective audit and reporting on the title and ownership of the IPR generated during the project. This will be done via periodic surveys (see Appendix 1) and reports based on the content of deliverables and partners assigned to the associated tasks. The IPO nominated by the project will conduct Interim IPR Audit will identify the Results generated by the project, its dependencies on and External IP, or Background knowledge, and recommend actions to be taken by the consortium for its protection. CEIT has allocated a specific budget to appoint the IPO. The results of the Interim IPR Audit carried out will be reported internally and the results of the Final IPR Audit carried out at M36 will be reported in the corresponding deliverable. The IPR Officer is Dr. Isabel Hernando, Professor of Civil Law at University of the Basque Country and IP Lawyer.

7.3 FINAL IP AND GENERATED FOREGROUND CONTROL REPORT.

The Final Report will summarize the results - foreground generated by each partner during the AIOSAT Project. During the periodic Reports all partners will be requested by the Intellectual Property Officer to identify:

- The **access rights** granted to another partner of the consortium of their background, which was needed for the implementation of the project.
- The **access rights** granted to another partner of the consortium of their foreground, which was needed for the implementation of the project.
- The **background** used in the implementation of the project.
- The **foreground** generated in the project.
- The **Party exploitable foreground** generated in the project where are identified the Consortium **Single Products** (SP) per Parties and their Contributions – components.

Moreover, the partners will also identify in these Interim Reports the commercial and open source software as well as the hardware used in the implementation of the project. The Intellectual Property Officer will review all these information and will provide advice about IPR when needed to the consortium. All this information will be requested using the “Result and IP Control Report Template” provided by the IPO.

Once all the IP information has been gathered from the partners, the IPO will carry out an objective audit and will report on the title and ownership of the IPR generated during the project. Tables available will be used to clearly identify the main outcomes of the IPR analysis. Among the foreground generated in AIOSAT during the Project, a **Table 1** will identify those that are exploitable foreground of the consortium classified in five groups (1) for Further Research; (2) for developing, creating and marketing a product/process; (3) for creating and providing a service; (4) for Standardization activities; and (5) For others (as Joint ventures, Spin-off, licensing, etc.). A **Table 2** will provide the possible and recommended IPR qualifications for the identified AIOSAT Exploitable Foreground. This Table will present the list of IPR registration applied or recommended. A **Table 3** will identify the Ownership percentages to the components – contributions to the Single Products and the Intermediate Single products developed in the AIOSAT Project and finally, for the Exploitable Foreground, a **Table 4** will identify the Parties ownership percentages to the Final Project Single products

7.4 EXPLOITATION AND OWNERSHIP AGREEMENT

Title and ownership of results is considered to be, from a legal perspective, a matter of undisputable fact. The IPR audits will be presented by the IPO to each partner as a proposal of ownership of results according to data provided by the Partners and derived from the control of technical outputs and deliverables for revision and acceptance by their organizations.

At the end of the AIOSAT project, these audits will form the basis for a potential Exploitation and Ownership Agreement (EOA) if any. This agreement will not be a formal project deliverable and is a private contract between partners in the same level as the Consortium Agreement. The Exploitation and Ownership Agreement will be a binding legal contract between the partners which will be negotiated and approved by authorized representatives within the partners' organizations.

8 PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION

8.1 COMPLIANCE WITH DATA PROTECTION DIRECTIVE 95/46/EC

Within the AIOSAT Project, the research activities and treatment of personal data will be conducted in compliance with the EU and National laws and Regulations on data Protection in force at the beginning of the Project and those that are scheduled to come into force in the period 2018 – 2020.

Personal Data is defined by European Directive 95/46/EC, Article 2 as:

‘Personal data’ shall mean any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identification number or to one or more factors specific to his physical, physiological, mental, economic, cultural or social identity.’

In the same way article 4(1) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) that will apply from 25 May 2018 defines Personal Data:

“personal data’ means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person”).

Furthermore, Article 10 Directive 95/46/EC states that:

*“1. Member States shall prohibit the processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade-union membership, and the processing of data concerning health or sex life”.
“2. Paragraph 1 shall not apply where: (a) the data subject has given his explicit consent to the processing of those data, except where the laws of the Member State provide that the prohibition referred to in paragraph 1 may not be lifted by the data subject’s giving his consent”.*

And article 9 of the (GDPR) sets up in its paragraphs 1 and 2 that:

1. “Processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning

health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.”

2.”Paragraph 1 shall not apply if one of the following applies:

(a) the data subject has given explicit consent to the processing of those personal data for one or more specified purposes, except where Union or Member State law provide that the prohibition referred to in paragraph 1 may not be lifted by the data subject

(j) processing is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1)

The personal data is therefore classified as sensitive personal data, and more general personal data.

Within the AIOSAT Project, sensitive personal data are completely excluded. Partners collecting general personal data are limited to: TSC and FRS. These data will be pseudonymized at capture. For further processing, these data will be either pseudonymized or anonymised.

In the AIOSAT Project, results are ultimately for the benefit of the society. Considering that Data fully anonymized are outside the scope of application of the data protection law, the research goals that include the collection, storage, consultation of pseudonymized data that may be of a natural person, raises immediate and justifiable concerns around the protection of personal data include the need to ensure that the personal data as project results are not misused.

Partners processing such anonymised or pseudonymized data are CEIT, RMA, INTEGR, INE, SAXION. Considering that, according to Article 1 (GDPR), “Pseudonymisation” means the “processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person” and “Processing” means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction”.

In the AIOSAT Project, every Partner is subject to national data protection laws derived from the transposition of the EU Data protection Directive, including the mandates of the Article 29 Working Group. The legislation of each participating Partner’s country enshrines the following key principles.

- Data must be processed fairly and lawfully.
- Data must be processed only for one or more specified and lawful purpose.
- Data must be adequate, relevant and not excessive for those purposes.
- Data must be accurate and kept up to date - data subjects have the right to have inaccurate personal data corrected or destroyed if the personal information is inaccurate to any matter of fact.
- Data must be kept for no longer than is necessary for the purposes it is being processed.
- Data must be processed in line with the rights of individuals - this includes the right to be informed of all the information held about them, to prevent processing of their personal information for marketing purposes, and to compensation if they can prove they have been damaged by a data controller's non-compliance with the Act.

- Data must be secured against accidental loss, destruction or damage and against unauthorized or unlawful processing - this applies to you even if your business uses a third party to process personal information on your behalf.
- Data must be not transferred to countries outside the European Economic Area without consent.

Furthermore, AIOSAT will comply with the H2020 Guidelines on Ethical Standards in Research and comply with ethical principles. sent or adoption of other adequate protection measures.

8.2 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

8.2.1 DMP Coordinator and Data Protection Supervisor

The DMP coordinator, CEIT, as Leader of Task Data Management Plan, is responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised. In the AIOSAT Project, CEIT (project Coordinator and DMP Leader as Data Supervisor) shall verify the consortium guarantees the treatment of personal data, pseudonymized or not, generated during the project. Within the consortium, CEIT's Iñigo Adin will be the point of contact for Data Protection issue and will coordinate the actions required to liaise between different Partners and will also be charge with providing opinion on the consortium's data protection compliance.

8.2.2 DMP Participants

As established in the Consortium Agreement (CA) 11.3, each party has to comply with all obligations and requirements of its corresponding national data protection legislation and the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC (or GDPR), and to provide all legal documents and certifications strictly required for compliance with such legislation to the Consortium designated Party for data protection supervision. Furthermore, the parties have agreed to H2020 MGA Art. 29 and compliance with EU Directive 0824/2009.

If Personal Data is involved and/or needed during the implementation of the Action and/or for any Exploitation activities, each partner, who provides or otherwise make available to any other Party such Personal Data ("Contributor"), shall notify this disclosure to the Consortium Data Protection Supervisor and represents that: (i) it has the authority and/or the authorization to disclose the such Information, (ii) it has obtained appropriate informed consents from the individuals involved, or from any other applicable institution, all in compliance with applicable regulations; and (iii) there is no restriction in place that would prevent any such other partner from using the such data in accordance with and for the purpose of the task in the AIOSAT Project. Partners will be required to have adequate security measures in place, both technical and operational.

8.2.3 DMP responsibilities

The responsibilities for the personal data depend on which EU State has jurisdiction over the data owner Partner and the subsequent data processing activities in the AIOSAT Project. The AIOSAT Project is itself not a legal entity. Thus, the responsibility for data protection will fall on the Partner of AIOSAT who is the “*Controller*”, the entity which collects and owns the data in question. When this contributor Partner is granting access rights over these personal data to other AIOSAT Partners, the recipient Partner is a “*Processor*” that will use the data only for carrying out specific processing activities as specified by the controller Partner. Thus, the decisive factor is which entity collected the data. Each of these Parties is responsible for notifying its local data protection authority.

8.3 DATA ACQUISITION / PROCESSING UNDER INFORMED CONSENT

8.3.1 Informed Consent – Preliminary considerations

Contributor Partner in AIOSAT Project will give sufficient advice on exactly which information must be provided to test participants and estimate which arrangements (insurance, exceptional licenses, etc.) are necessary. In order to conclude a contract/letter of agreement with test participants, such knowledge on the exact test design and testing procedure is will be provided. A Consent Form is provided in Annex 1

8.3.2 Informed consent. Information provided to test participants

In order to obtain a valid consent from the test subject to log data and allow for safe participation in the Tests (T), information on the testing procedure and setup must be comprehensive. The participants do not need to understand the underlying technology in detail, but do need to understand the implications of the technology for them so that they can assume an informed responsibility. This will make clear what information is necessary and which kind of data is being logged, who will have access and how it shall be processed.

In case the T is taken out under real-life conditions and without further surveillance, a great amount of information on safe use is needed. The information should be provided in a way that the least informed test-participant, who is therefore most exposed to a danger, can participate safely. The possibility to ask questions at any time later during the T will be provided.

It is legally required that the test participants know which data is being logged. It should also be pointed out, which conclusions can be drawn from the data available (as far as possibly foreseeable) and this should involve all imaginable data sources and their combination (including external sources that can be resorted to). The meaning of anonymisation and pseudonymisation as well as any other measures to assure data privacy should also be described. In the case that data is being dissociated or anonymised, it must be pointed out at which point of data processing this is realised.

8.3.3 Informed Consent. Consent of test participants and incidental findings

Based on the provision that data acquisition and processing is generally discouraged, the most important exception from this rule for Ts is the consent of the person concerned. In the case where data is collected in circumstances in which consent may not be obtained, all measures must be taken to de-identify the data and provide a means of redress to those who make a valid and reasonable request to the project.

For any consent given in terms of data acquisition, processing or use, the person concerned must:

- Make this statement in written form or suitable analogue (unless under certain specific circumstances),
- The consequences must be clarified (intended purpose of acquisition, processing and use), including the consequences, if consent is not given,
- The consent must even be especially highlighted, if the consent to data acquisition, processing and use is issued together with other statements
- Consent must always be given voluntarily, even in the case of Test Participants who are employees or contractors of the Partners and are involved as part of their assignment to the project

An issue of increasing importance in research which involves human beings is the matter of “incidental findings.” Incidental findings have been defined as observations of potential significance unexpectedly discovered in research participants and unrelated to the purpose of the study or research.

The probability and potential for incidental findings in AIOSAT Project is considered by the consortium to be low as the research will primarily monitor activities in the validation and field test of project results. The Test Participants will not be directly observed. All participants will have immediate access to their incidental- related data before it is anonymised and this eliminating the possibility of reporting incidental findings to a specific test participant. In order to address the potential for Incidental Findings the Informed Consent Form provided in Annex 1 to this document has includes a section on Incidental Findings.

8.4 CONCLUSIONS

This document presents the internal guidelines that will be followed for the appropriate data and privacy management of the AIOSAT project. Some of the sections in this document will be updated throughout the lifetime of the project, as previously indicated, in order to appropriately addresses the practical requirements of the project. The overall data and privacy management plan of the project described in this deliverable is aligned with the information already provided in the Description of Action for AIOSAT (as per Grant Agreement number 776425).

ANNEX 1. Test Participant INFORMATION SHEET (DATED OF 2018 (version 1)

(Subject Participants need to be provided with copy of document ANNEX.1. in THEIR official languages and signed in each page

TITLE OF PROJECT: AIOSAT PROJECT (AUTONOMOUS INDOOR –
OUTDOOR SAFETY TRACKING SYSTEM
Funding: European Union Horizon 2020 - (GA nº 690238)
Duration: 2017- 2020
Coordinator: CEIT-IK4 (Spain)
Principal Investigator at local level _____
Name and Surname: _____
Signature : _____
Institution conducting the test at
local level : _____

Institutional address : _____
Institutional Telephone: (.....)

Institutional Email: (.....)

Other research Partners involved in the Project: RMA (Belgium), INTEGR (Spain), INE (Netherlands),
SAXION (Netherlands),

1.- Introduction

I would like to invite you to take part in this research project. Before you decide if you wish to take part in this study we would like you to understand the purpose of the research and what your contribution would be.

Please carefully read the following information and do not hesitate to ask questions about any aspect of the study.

2.- Aim of the Study

The AIOSAT project aims to develop a technology system to improve current fire responder safety when operating in environments with harsh signal propagation conditions solving existing needs.

- To enable a high availability and high integrity team positioning and tracking system able to work inside buildings and rural areas.
- To develop a set of tracking and alerting application protocols for fire services which improve responder safety during fire suppression operations within structures and forest environments.
- To reduce the impact of fires on health, environment and economy

3.- Participants in the Study

The participation in the study is voluntary. You are perfectly welcome to say “no” to taking part and will be placed under no pressure to change your mind. If you would like to participate, you may also withdraw from the study at any point without consequence.

You may also decide to withdraw your data at any stage.

The participants aimed are:

1. Able bodied adult (18 years of age or older)
2. Project researchers and /or staff participating on a voluntary basis that comply with the conditions of 1 above
3. Professional fire-fighters linked to the project partners

4. Incidental Findings

Although the purpose of the research is the testing and evaluation of technologies linked to test participant, there is a remote possibility that in the analysis of the research data an incidental finding relating the physical or physiological health of the participant may occur. In this event the participant will be informed of the finding in confidence and as a private person unless there is an explicit indication by the participant they do not wish to be informed.

5. Privacy and Confidentiality

If you agree to take part in the study, you will be asked to sign the consent form below to grant access to your data which were captured during the test. All the process (as example: collection, recording, use and transmission) of your data shall be carry out according to the national law applicable to the institution conducting the test at local level below where you can exercise your data protection rights: access, rectification, erasure, to object, portability.

If you agree to take part in the study, with the exception of the authorized research participants of your own institution conducting the test at local level below that will have access to your identification, all your data will be sent and use pseudonymised (using a code rather) and /or fully anonymised (never related to your identity) by the others research participants. This ensures the maximum possible privacy protection for your data. Once you freely agree to participate in the research, you will receive a code-number, and from that moment on all personal data are under that code. Therefore, the analysis of the results will be anonymous, that is no one will know who the data belongs to. The information will be processed during the analysis of the data obtained and will appear in the project deliverables - but again, only in a way that will not allow anybody to identify from whom we received the information assuring in every moment compliance with applicable legislation.

Your personal data are kept in a secured Data Base and in a confidential manner for a 5 year period after the end of the Project which it is removed from any storage. Nevertheless, Research Parties involved in the AIOSAT Project may used the data fully anonymised (never related to your identity) in further research, publications or presented in scientific conferences.

6. Risk and Limitations

The data test are being collected as part of your professional routine. Therefore, you will not be exposed to any increased physical risk or harm. *(If necessary, the participant will be provided with a written statement of potential risks and limitations limitation and protocol for action in the event of failure before tests begin. If necessary, they will also be given a full briefing by the project staff).*

7. Applicable national law

Applicable national laws are the corresponding at the site where the data is being collected by the **Institution conducting the test at local level:**

- *(INCLUDE HERE NAME AND NUMBER OF THE SPECIFIC NATIONAL LAW)*

8. Applicable European legislation:

- DIRECTIVE 95/46/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data
- REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (in May 2018)

9. What happens now?

If you do wish to take part in this study, you will be asked to sign the below consent form. If you decide not to take part it will not affect you in any way. You can change your mind at any time and withdraw from the study. Thank you for your time and for considering the possibility of taking part in this research.

CONSENT FORM FOR SUBJECT PARTICIPATION IN RESEARCH

Subject Participant [*Name and Surname, national identification number (if any).....*]

- | | Please Tick |
|--|-------------|
| • I confirm I have been given and have read and understood the Subject Participant Information sheet (dated of 2018 version 1) for the above study and have asked and received answers to any questions raised. | [] |
| • I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason and without my rights being affected in anyway. | [] |
| • I understand that the researchers will hold all data collected securely and in confidence and that all efforts will be made to ensure that I cannot be identified as a participant in the study (except as might be required by law) and I give my permission for the researchers to hold this data. | [] |
| • I do not wish to be informed of any incidental findings | |
| • I understand that I have the right to withdraw my data at any time, by contacting (<i>insert name of clinical manager at local site</i>) where I can exercise my data protection rights | [] |
| • I understand that if I have a complaint about AIOSAT Project, I should contact (<i>insert name of contact in the Party conducting the test at local level and identification of the supervisory authority</i>) | |
| • I agree to take part in the above study. | |
| • I agree to my data being securely and safely transferred for data processing [to partners of AIOSAT Project: RMA (Belgium), INTEGR (Spain), INE (Netherlands), SAXION (Netherlands),] to help develop the AIOSAT system. | [] |
| • I agree to fully anonymised data being used for scientific research purposes, scientific conferences including inclusions of the data in publications. | [] |

I understand that I am entitled to and will be given a copy of this signed Consent Form.

Name of the Subject Participant

Signature

Date

